

Hierarchical Bayesian Calibration Toward Credible Fill Gas Mixture Conductivity Predictions

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ABSTRACT

We present a joint, hierarchically pooled calibration of a gas-mixture thermal-conductivity model used in nuclear fuel performance analysis. The method couples pure- and mixed-gas datasets so that uncertainty remains coherent across compositions while allowing experiment-specific effects to be partially pooled through shared hyperparameters. We construct predictive intervals that envelop code-to-measurement residuals independent of whether they arise from measurement noise or model inadequacy, and we propagate uncertainty end-to-end, from calibrated coefficients to posterior-predictive conductivities relevant to gap conductance models. Inference is performed via a Metropolis-Hastings (MH)-within-Gibbs sampler wrapped around a Gaussian process (GP) surrogate, enabling computational efficiency at modest sample sizes and accommodating heterogeneous experimental sources without degrading accuracy. Sensitivity analyses indicate that predictive performance is largely insensitive to the amount of calibration data and to calibration/validation splits, reflecting the stabilizing effect of hierarchical pooling. Overall, the joint calibration improves agreement with measurements while preserving physical coherence across compositions and providing transparent uncertainty quantification suitable for downstream evaluations.

Keywords: Hierarchical, Bayesian, Gas mixture, Thermal conductivity, Gap conductance

1. INTRODUCTION

In this study, we develop a joint calibration framework for fill-gas thermal conductivity used in gap-conductance models for nuclear fuel. Traditional practice calibrates pure-gas correlations stage-wise (separately for each gas) and then inserts them into a mixture formulation [1]. While simple and modular, stage-wise fitting can break uncertainty coherence across compositions and misallocate bias in mixtures. We instead infer all gas-specific coefficients simultaneously using both single- and multi-component datasets. This promotes physical consistency, exploits cross-gas correlation, and produces more reliable uncertainty quantification for mixture predictions. We first present the mixture-conductivity formulation (Section 2), then the experimental dataset (Section 3), followed by the calibration methodology (Section 4); results and analysis demonstrate the advantages of the joint approach (Section 5), and we conclude with key findings (Section 6).

2. GAS MIXTURE THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY

Transport properties of gas mixtures are described by kinetic-theory formulations for viscosity and thermal conductivity. Because these expressions are often impractical, approximations derived from

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rigorous theory are commonly used. Under the rigid-sphere assumption, Ref. [2] provides a closed-form expression for the mixture thermal conductivity, referenced in Equation (1). The coefficients used in Equation (1b) are estimated in Ref. [3].

$$k_{\text{mix}} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{k_i}{1 + \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^n \psi_{ij} \frac{x_j}{x_i}}, \quad (1a)$$

with

$$\psi_{ij} = \phi_{ij} \left[1 + 2.41 \frac{(M_i - M_j)(M_i - 0.142M_j)}{(M_i + M_j)^2} \right] \quad (1b)$$

$$\phi_{ij} = \frac{\left[1 + \left(\frac{k_i}{k_j} \right)^{1/2} \left(1 + \frac{M_i}{M_j} \right)^{1/4} \right]^2}{2\sqrt{2} \left(1 + \frac{M_i}{M_j} \right)^{1/2}} \quad (1c)$$

where n is the number of components in mixture, M is the molecular weight, x is the mole fraction, and k is the thermal conductivity of each individual gas (W/m-K), expressed as:

$$k = aT^b \quad (2)$$

where T is the temperature (K), and a, b are the empirical coefficients tabulated in Table I.

3. EXPERIMENTAL DATA

The dataset of Ref. [4] spans monatomic gases (He, Ne, Ar, Kr, Xe) and their binary/ternary mixtures. We analyze the corresponding thermal-conductivity measurements to quantify composition-dependent trends and variability. In total, 713 measurements across all compositions are included in this study. The temperature coverage extends from 73–2500 K for single-component gases, up to 793 K for binary mixtures, and at 311 K for ternary mixtures. Distributions for the measured compositions are shown in Figure 1. To visualize distributional features, we use violin plots: each violin depicts a probability density, with width proportional to local data density. This representation makes skewness and multimodal clustering within mixtures readily visible and exposes differences in data coverage across sampled composition combinations. The analysis is restricted to the low-pressure data, where thermal conductivity is only a function of temperature.

4. METHODOLOGY

We perform joint *hierarchical* Bayesian calibration (partial-pooling across experiments) to assess impacts on predictive accuracy, uncertainty coverage, and bias transfer to mixtures. Following Refs. [5, 6, 7], model inadequacy and nuisance effects are captured by experiment-specific latent parameters λ drawn from a common population assumed to be Gaussian over all experiments. This induces partial pooling and yields posterior inference for population hyperparameters (μ, σ) and experiment-level coefficients $\{\lambda_{i,aj}, \lambda_{i,bj}\}$ for $j \in \{\text{He, Ne, Ar, Kr, Xe}\}$ in Equation (2) together with $\{\lambda_{i,\theta_1}, \lambda_{i,\theta_2}\}$ in Equation (1b). We denote the calibrated mixture model by \mathcal{M}^{mix} (see Equation (1)), which composes the calibrated single-gas submodels \mathcal{M}^j (see Equation (2)) and $\mathcal{M}^{\psi_{ij}}$ (see Equation (1b)). In total, 12 parameters are estimated jointly within this framework, as shown in Figure 2. In this work, the Bayesian formulation is supported by Gaussian process (GP) surrogates that replace the computationally expensive simulation models, with one independent GP constructed for each experiment. Although the present model is simple enough to be calibrated directly, the GP framework is introduced here to enable scalability and to support more complex models in future applications.

Figure 1. Distributions of experimental thermal conductivity data represented as violin plots for gas combinations: (a) single-component data; (b) binary mixtures; and (c) ternary mixtures of monatomic gases (He, Ne, Ar, Kr, and Xe). Each violin depicts the probability density of measured values, with the width proportional to the frequency of occurrence. Individual measurements are indicated in black, medians in blue, and means in orange. Central markers indicate the median (blue) and mean (red). Plotting is restricted to measured compositions. The value N displayed above each violin denotes the number of measurements for the corresponding gas composition.

GP surrogates were built using 50 design points generated via Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) in Dakota[8] over the calibration-parameter space. Parameters were perturbed around their nominal values using Gaussian draws with a 10% standard deviation, $\mathcal{N}(\mu_\theta, [0.1\mu_\theta]^2)$, where μ_θ are the means listed in Table I. For each sampled parameter set, model outputs were computed at all 713 measurement conditions. The resulting dataset was randomly divided into 80% for calibration and 20% for independent validation.

With the GP-surrogates in place, the hierarchical posterior distribution is explored using a blocked Metropolis–Hastings–within–Gibbs (MH–within–Gibbs) sampler, which alternately updates the latent variables and the hyperparameters. Following this sampling, the posterior predictive distribution (marginalized posterior) is obtained by forward propagation through the assumed Gaussian hierarchical relationships. Rather than using a fixed calibration–validation split, the analysis is repeated for different partition ratios to assess the robustness of the method (as described in Section 5).

5. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

In hierarchical Bayesian calibration, experiment-specific parameters are treated as draws from population-level hyperparameters, inducing partial pooling across experiments. Consequently, posterior and posterior-predictive estimates are primarily governed by the shared hyperparameters rather than any particular calibration/validation split, rendering performance largely insensitive to the partition. This insensitivity is evident in Figure 3, which plots normalized calibrated parameters as a function of the calibration fraction (with the remainder held out for validation). Likewise, Figure 4 shows the posteriors of the calibrated parameters conditioned on the calibration/validation split; the hierarchical Bayesian approach yields consistent and well-identified posterior means across splits.

The marginal posteriors of the calibrated parameters are summarized as a corner plot in Figure 5, and their corresponding summary statistics are provided in Table I, together with the original parameter values. In our results, the rings are approximately circular across parameter pairs, indicating weak pairwise dependence (i.e., parameters are effectively uncorrelated in the posterior).

Figure 6a compares predictions using the original coefficients with measurements; neon and its mixtures are excluded due to unavailable thermal-conductivity coefficients for neon (see Table I). Figure 6b

Figure 2. Bayesian networks for joint calibration: the plate replicates experiments i , with local (experiment-specific) parameters λ and the governing model \mathcal{M}^{mix} inside, and global hyperparameters outside. Solid edges denote probabilistic dependencies; dashed edges denote deterministic relations. Shaded nodes are observed; unshaded nodes are latent.

Figure 3. Sensitivity analysis on calibration/validation split for normalized calibrated parameters using hierarchical Bayesian framework. Normalization is defined as the ratio of the calibrated parameter at a given split to its value under the 100% calibration (no validation) baseline.

shows predictions based on coefficients estimated via joint hierarchical Bayesian calibration, together with the calibrated models and their $\pm 1\sigma$ prediction intervals. These intervals reflect both parameter uncertainty and a 5% measurement uncertainty. Joint calibration improves agreement and yields a more symmetric distribution about the $P = M$ line, with particularly notable improvements for Ar and Kr.

Figure 4. Sensitivity analysis on calibration/validation split for calibrated parameters using hierarchical Bayesian framework. The plotted distributions show posterior estimates from this study (see Table I); color intensity encodes the fraction of data used for calibration (darker = larger calibration set). The orange dashed vertical line indicates the original values from Table I and is shown only when it lies within the x-axis limits.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This work applies a hierarchical Bayesian calibration framework, combining Gibbs sampling with Metropolis–Hastings (MH-within-Gibbs) updates and a GP surrogate, to a widely used gas-mixture thermal-conductivity model in nuclear fuel performance codes. We jointly calibrate all gas-specific coefficients using both single- and multi-component datasets. This enables physical coherence, leverages cross-gas correlation, and produces more reliable uncertainty quantification than stage-wise approaches that first fit pure-gas correlations independently and then insert them into a mixture formulation. The resulting predictive intervals are constructed to envelop code-to-measurement residuals regardless of their origin (e.g., measurement noise or model inadequacy). Although demonstrated here on separate-effects data, the method effectively handles strong nonlinearities and is well-suited for industrial deployment. It remains computationally efficient at modest sample sizes and accommodates heterogeneous experimental data sources without degrading accuracy. Sensitivity analysis of the calibrated parameters corroborates this, showing that predictive performance is largely insensitive to the calibration sample size.

Figure 5. Marginalized posterior of the calibration parameters: diagonal plots show marginal histograms; and off-diagonal plots show joint scatter with probability-density rings. Interpreting the probability-density rings: tilted, elongated ellipses indicate substantial pairwise correlation (the tilt's sign gives the correlation sign), whereas near-circular rings indicate negligible correlation. Axis-aligned elongation (horizontal or vertical) reflects unequal marginal variances and does not, by itself, imply correlation.

Table I. Summary statistics of the marginalized posterior for each parameter ($\pm 1\sigma$)

	Calibration parameter	Original [†]	Joint calibration (this study)	
			mean	± 1 std
Helium (4.002602 g/mol)	cal_a_He	3.366×10^{-3}	2.813×10^{-3}	6.319×10^{-5}
	cal_b_He	0.668	0.7029	3.190×10^{-3}
Neon (20.1797 g/mol)	cal_a_Ne	n/a	9.118×10^{-4}	1.601×10^{-5}
	cal_b_Ne	n/a	0.6963	2.308×10^{-3}
Argon (39.948 g/mol)	cal_a_Ar	3.421×10^{-4}	2.964×10^{-4}	4.451×10^{-6}
	cal_b_Ar	0.701	0.7178	4.422×10^{-3}
Krypton (83.798 g/mol)	cal_a_Kr	4.726×10^{-5}	8.089×10^{-5}	2.256×10^{-6}
	cal_b_Kr	0.923	0.8328	4.132×10^{-3}
Xenon (131.293 g/mol)	cal_a_Xe	4.0288×10^{-5}	4.410×10^{-5}	7.723×10^{-7}
	cal_b_Xe	0.872	0.8635	9.341×10^{-3}
Equation (1b)	cal_fij_theta1	2.41	2.448	4.771×10^{-2}
Equation (1b)	cal_fij_theta2	0.142	0.140355	2.4815×10^{-3}

[†] as reported in MATPRO-11 [1]

(a) Predictions using the original coefficients

 (b) Joint calibration predictions with ± 1 standard deviations

Figure 6. Comparison of model predictions with measurements: (a) using the original coefficients (as reported in MATPRO-11 [1]) and (b) using coefficients estimated through joint hierarchical Bayesian calibration.

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